

NDAC/LO/150
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Comparison of FAST and NDAC 30 months sphere solutions
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1. OVERVIEW OF DATA

FAST SPHERE SOLUTION 30 MONTH (tape sent to Lund on 5 October):

Number of RGCs: 1914 (orbit 48 to 2129)
Number of observations: 3221747
Number of stars observed: 118399

Selection of stars for comparison:

- 1- Stars without astrometric solutions
==> rejected stars 181
- 2- Double stars with differential and absolute astrometric solutions
==> rejected stars 6796
- 3- Stars with too large residuals (chi_2 test)
==> rejected stars 10682
- 4- The two coefficients of correlation between parallax and p.m. > 0.6
==> rejected stars 333
- 5- The formal parallax error is > 4 mas
==> rejected stars 323
- 6- star with grid step problem (no solution)
==>rejected stars 134

Number of stars retained: 99950

NDAC SPHERE SOLUTION 30 MONTH (tape sent to CERGA on 22 September):

Identified by the NDAC/LO sphere solution run number 204.

Number of RGCs: 1963 (orbit 1 to 2118)
Number of observations: 3158933
Number of stars observed: 113278 (+ 4858 routed to DS)

Orbits included: 1 to 2118 (incl), in all 1963 RGCs
Total number of observations: 3158933
Total number of stars: 113278

Stars with < 6 observations: 119 (remaining: 113159)
Stars with too large residuals: 9405 (remaining: 103754)
Stars with deviating positions *) 49 (remaining: 103705)
Stars with sigma_par > 4 mas: 487 (remaining: 103218)
Stars with corr > 0.6: 87 (remaining: 103131)

*) based on a comparison with RGO (starmapper) positions.

Number of stars retained: 103131

The intersection FAST+NDAC 30 months contains 95579 stars, on which all following comparisons are based.

2. ORIENTATION DIFFERENCES RELATIVE TO FK5

For 1210 stars in common between FAST, NDAC and FK5, the orientation and rotation components, at epoch 1991.25 and in the equatorial frame, are:

	r_x	r_y	r_z	v_x	v_y	v_z
FAST - FK5	2.761	20.979	-37.295	-0.089	0.816	-3.567
NDAC - FK5	18.281	33.903	-47.914	0.921	-1.072	-0.364
diff (N-F)	15.520	12.924	-10.619	1.010	-1.888	3.203

Uncertainties in the components of r and v are 3.4 mas and 0.10 mas/yr. The rms residuals are 115 mas and 3.4 mas/yr. [In the 18 months comparison the rms residuals were 117 mas and 5.0 mas/yr. NDAC/LO/148 by mistake gave the mean absolute residuals here, or a factor 0.80 smaller numbers.]

3. ORIENTATION DIFFERENCES NDAC - FAST

At epoch 1991.25 the mean rotation vectors are:

$$r = \begin{pmatrix} +15.628 (.004) \\ +13.574 (.003) \\ -11.081 (.004) \end{pmatrix} \quad v = \begin{pmatrix} +0.898 (.004) \\ -1.818 (.004) \\ +3.056 (.009) \end{pmatrix}$$

The rms residuals are 1.12 mas and 1.57 mas/yr [18 months: 1.70 mas and 3.42 mas/yr].

Separating the stars according to colour we find:

	N	r_x	r_y	r_z	v_x	v_y	v_z
B-V<0.7	49004	15.538	13.606	-11.083	1.101	-1.888	3.054
		.006	.005	.006	.007	.007	.011
B-V>0.7	46575	15.736	13.538	-11.082	0.657	-1.749	3.075
		.007	.004	.008	.009	.007	.013
diff		-0.198	0.068	-0.001	0.444	-0.139	-0.021
diff/sd		-21.5	+10.6	-0.1	+38.9	-14.0	-1.2

Comment: The differences in mas and mas/yr are only slightly smaller than was found in the 18 months comparison (NDAL/LO/148, Table 3):

diff (18 months)	-0.421	0.149	0.025	0.613	-0.186	0.059
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This suggests that the same mechanism is still at work, only with a reduced amplitude due to the higher accumulated weight of the data.

4. POSITION AND P.M. DIFFERENCES AFTER ROTATION

At epoch 1991.25, and after removing the rotation difference from Section 3, the two largest differences in position were 79 mas (HIC 64241) and 39 mas (HIC 24186). There are only 12 stars with position differences exceeding 20 mas. Thus, there is for the first time no grid-step difference in the data.

The RMS difference in RA*cos(Dec) is 1.275 mas [cf. 1.636 mas for the 18 months solutions], and in Dec 1.038 mas [1.359 mas]. The 'improvement factor' is about 0.77 in both coordinates.

In proper motion the RMS differences are 1.836 mas/yr [3.857 mas/yr] and 1.456 mas/yr [3.248 mas/yr]. The 'improvement factor' is about 0.46.

5. PARALLAX DIFFERENCES

For the parallaxes, the RMS difference is 1.466 mas [1.956 mas]; the 'improvement factor' is here 0.75. The distribution of parallax differences is slightly asymmetric, and the median difference, -0.048 (+/- 0.005) mas is a bit larger than before [-0.008 mas for the 18 months].

Dividing the stars according to Dec, Hp and BT-VT, the median differences NDAC-FAST are as follows [values from 18 months in brackets]:

north - south	= +0.032 (.011)	[-0.052 (.014)]
bright - faint	= -0.027 (.011)	[-0.050 (.014)]
blue - red	= +0.005 (.011)	[+0.007 (.014)]

Some improvement is noted. That the north-south difference has changed sign (again: it was +0.3 mas for the 12 months comparison) supports the hypothesis that it is due to a lack of connection between the hemispheres, rather than a real difference in the reductions or data.

6. FORMAL ERRORS

The median formal errors in parallax and proper motion are shown below, with 18 months values in brackets:

	FAST	NDAC	NDAC/FAST
parallax	1.335 [1.705]	1.538 [1.956]	1.152 [1.147]
proper motion (major axis)	1.637 [3.258]	1.827 [3.679]	1.116 [1.129]

The ratio remains approximately the same, which is to be expected since

nothing has changed in the weighting systems of either consortium.

7. PARALLAX DISTRIBUTIONS

The parallax distributions for the 95579 stars are remarkably similar for FAST and NDAC. The number of negative values is 4350 for FAST and 4869 for NDAC, or 4.55% and 5.09% respectively. A weighted mean ($0.6 \cdot \pi_F + 0.4 \cdot \pi_N$) gives 3867 or 4.05% negative values [5.76% in the 18 months solution].

Three observations can be made from these numbers: First, that the 30 months parallaxes are really very much better than the 18 months. In fact it appears that the random errors continue to diminish with the square-root of the number of observations, as if we are still a long way from hitting a limit set by systematic errors in the data. Second, that a mean of FAST and NDAC parallaxes continues to be much better than either solution. Third, that the FAST parallaxes are, on the whole, marginally better than the NDAC parallaxes.